

INTERVIEW QUESTIONNAIRE

Introduction:

- **Quick intro of yourself and IEECP/RGI to the interviewee.**
- **Background of the study and its aim:** The study is conducted in the context of the “Public engagement for energy infrastructure” Task by Users-centred Energy Systems by the IEA. The task looks at effective public engagement in energy infrastructure projects. With the interviews, we want to investigate drivers and barriers of public engagement, as well as good practices of a successful participation in energy infrastructure. When we talk about energy infrastructure, we specifically mean energy production systems, such as wind turbines, solar panels, or biomass plants, and electricity grids, but you can also elaborate on assisting technologies, such as storage technologies or green hydrogen production systems. The results of the study will feed into a best practice guideline for practitioners and policymakers.
- **Data protection:** Thank you for agreeing to take part in this interview, which should last maximum one hour. Your participation in this interview is voluntary and you can change your mind at any time. The information that you provide will be treated in confidence by the research team. By conducting this interview, you are consenting to collection and processing of personal data for research purposes, which I sent you beforehand. Do you have any questions regarding that? We would like to record the discussion for analysis purposes, which will be used to help us accurately collect findings for the research. The recordings will be securely stored and retained by us and destroyed after the completion of the research. Are you happy for us to proceed?
- **I'll start the recording of our meeting now.**

Question for Member States-level actors only; Questions to EU or international experts only; Questions for the industrial/business interviewees; Note: an additional question might be added depending on the specific interview partner.

#	Question	Area of investigation / remark
0	Can you briefly explain me, what is your role at your organisation? • •	<i>Inro /About you</i>
1	When you hear the term “public engagement”. What does it mean to you?	<i>Meaning public participation</i>
2	What do you think are the different ways the <u>public should be engaged</u> in energy infrastructure developments?	<i>Ways of participation</i>

3	<p>Do you think it is <u>important</u> for the public to participate in energy infrastructure developments? And if yes, why would you say so? If they respond no: Why not?</p>	<i>Purpose of participation</i>
4a	<p>In COUNTRY, are there <u>mandatory or voluntary requirements</u>, such as laws or guidebooks, for public engagement on energy infrastructure projects? If so, what are those requirements and for what technologies. <i>Follow up questions, if not addressed:</i> - Why do you think there are requirements for X and Y and not for other technologies?</p>	<i>Legal frameworks</i>
4b	<p>If you think about different country contexts, are you aware of any <u>mandatory or voluntary requirements</u> in specific countries that you think are important to enable effective participation in energy infrastructure?</p>	<i>Legal frameworks</i>
5a	<p>What do you perceive as the <u>main drivers, or motivating factors</u>, for the public to engage with energy infrastructure developments? <i>Follow up questions, if not addressed:</i> - Can you think of other factors that could <u>motivate individuals or groups</u> to become or stay engaged? - Can you think of other drivers that come from the broader <u>national context and legal and institutional environment</u>, such as the enabling frameworks, or culture of participation? - Do you think that the current regulatory frameworks allow for a meaningful stakeholder engagement? If yes, why do you think so?</p>	<i>Drivers</i>
5b	<p>Do you think that the <u>current organisational structure</u> of your company helps to progress with a meaningful stakeholder engagement? Why? What shall be improved? <i>Follow up questions, if not addressed:</i> - Are there any internal policies in your organisation that promote sustained engagement with stakeholders? Could you elaborate? - What went well in engaging the public when running your daily business/implementing your project? And why would you say so? - Would you call that a driver?</p>	<i>Drivers</i>
6a	<p>Now let's move from drivers to barriers: What do you perceive as the <u>main barriers</u> to public engagement in energy infrastructure? <i>Follow up questions, if not addressed:</i></p>	<i>Barriers</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can you think of other barriers <u>preventing individuals or groups</u> from participating? - Can you think of other barriers that come from the <u>broader national context and legal and institutional environment</u>, such as the importance devoted to public participation in policymaking in general, or regulations and laws in place? - How do you think should policy or legal frameworks be designed to enable participation? 	
6b	<p>When running your daily business/ implementing your project, what, if anything, <u>is missing</u> when it comes to <u>involving the public</u>? Is there anything holding you back?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Would you call that a barrier? - If applicable: how could this barrier (or these barriers) be overcome? 	<i>Barriers</i>
6c	<p>Can you think of <u>any examples</u> you have experienced in your work, where <u>public opposition</u> to energy infrastructure developments was/is a barrier?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If applicable: do you think public opposition to, or protests against, energy infrastructure developments are different from other types of infrastructure? <p><i>Follow-up, if applicable: to what extent do you think it's different?</i></p>	<i>Barriers - example</i>
7	<p>What do you think are <u>suitable formats or methods</u> for engaging the public? Can you first name different formats and then we will discuss each of them.</p> <p><i>Follow up questions:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At which stage, or stages, of the project's development do you find it the most important to engage the public? - <u>Why</u> would you suggest applying method X, and what point in time? And who should lead the engagement process? OR <u>Why would you apply method X and at what point in time?</u> - What should specifically be achieved with such method? - What format or formats, do you think, are most <u>inclusive</u> in terms of participation and lead to <u>fair</u> energy infrastructure developments? And why would you say so? - After the COVID-19 outbreak many of the engagement formats moved <u>online</u>. How would you assess that this shift <u>impacted</u> a successful stakeholder engagement? 	<p><i>Formats / methods / objectives</i></p> <p><i>Why and when</i></p> <p><i>Justice aspects</i></p> <p><i>Levels of participation</i></p> <p><i>Justice aspects</i></p>
8	<p>If applicable, please could you tell me about <u>one specific energy infrastructure project</u> - in which you have been involved in, or that you are aware of - that you would say was successful in terms of how the public has been engaged?</p>	<i>Good practice</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How was the public effectively engaged within the project? What methods were used? - Were <u>community benefits</u> offered to the public, and how was the effect on the acceptability of the project? - If you reflect on the project <u>process</u>, what were the key <u>success factors</u> of the effective public engagement? - If you reflect on the project <u>outcomes</u>, to what extent do you think the public engagement has led to <u>different outcomes</u> than originally anticipated? Were these outcomes better or worse? 	
9	What would be one <u>key takeaway message</u> that you think is the most important thing that people should consider when engaging with the public on energy infrastructure projects?	<i>Take away</i>
10	Is there anything else relevant to the research that we did not already discuss? Is there anything else that you would like to add?	<i>Closing</i>
11	Can you recommend another person I should contact regarding the topic?	<i>Contacts</i>
12	We will analyse the interview according to the GDPR and confidentiality requirements. Do you want to be informed about the outcomes of the research?	<i>Further involvement: Results reporting</i>
13	We plan to conduct an online expert workshop on the topic in autumn/winter. Would you like to be invited to the workshop?	<i>Further involvement: Workshop</i>
14	We plan to develop a best practice guide for public participation. Would you like to be contacted to give feedback on the guideline?	<i>Further involvement: Guideline</i>

Thank you very much for the interview!